

How to make HEPData input

A how-to guide designed for legacy analyses

There are many ways to do this. My goal here is to show you the quickest.

Video tutorial available [here](#)

How to use these slides

Commands and code:

```
git clone https://github.com/tkrobatsch/YAML_Maker.git
```

Assignment:

Assignment: Make a HEPData account

Indicates we will wait for most people to catch up

What is HEPData?

A repository for data

Measurement of jet-medium interactions via direct photon-hadron correlations in Au+Au and d+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV

The PHENIX collaboration: Acharya, U., Adare, A., Afanador, S., Aidala, C., Ajitanand, N.N., Akiba, Y., Akimoto, R., Al-Bataineh, H., Alexander, J., ...

Phys.Rev.C 102 (2020) 054910, 2020. https://doi.org/10.17182/hepdata.101752

Journal INSPIRE Resources

Abstract (data abstract): BNL-RHIC. We present direct photon-hadron correlations in 200 GeV/Au+Au, d+Au and p+p collisions, for direct photon p_T from 3-12 GeV/c, collected by the PHENIX Collaboration in the years from 2006 to 2011. We observe no significant modification of jet fragmentation in d+Au collisions, indicating that cold nuclear matter effects are small or absent. Hadrons carrying a large fraction of the quark momentum are suppressed in Au+Au compared to p+p and d+Au. As the momentum fraction decreases, the yield of hadrons in Au+Au increases to an excess over the yield in p+p collisions. The excess is at large angles and at low hadron p_T , and is most pronounced for hadrons associated with lower momentum direct photons. Comparison to theoretical calculations suggests that the hadron excess arises from medium response to energy deposited by jets.

Figure 2: Per-trigger yield of hadrons associated to direct photons in Au+Au collisions for direct photon p_T 5-9 GeV/c, compared with p+p...

Figure 3: Per-trigger yield of hadrons associated to direct photons in d+Au collisions for direct photon p_T 7-9 GeV/c, compared with p+p...

Figure 4a: Integrated away-side $y_{10} - \bar{y}$ per-trigger yields of Au+Au, d+Au, and p+p, as a function of ξ .

Figure 4b: Integrated away-side $y_{10} - \bar{y}$ per-trigger I_{AA} and I_{dA} of Au+Au, d+Au, and p+p, as a function of ξ .

Figure 5a: I_{AA} vs ξ for direct photon p_T^0 of 5-7 GeV/c, 7-9 GeV/c, and 9-12 GeV/c.

Figure 5b: I_{dA} vs ξ for direct photon p_T^0 of 5-7 GeV/c, 7-9 GeV/c, and 9-12 GeV/c.

Figure 5c: I_{AA} vs ξ for direct photon p_T^0 of 5-7 GeV/c, 7-9 GeV/c, and 9-12 GeV/c.

Figure 6a: I_{AA} as a function of ξ for direct photon p_T^0 of 5-7, 7-9, and 9-12 GeV/c. Three away-side integration ranges...

Figure 6b: I_{AA} as a function of ξ for direct photon p_T^0 of 5-7, 7-9, and 9-12 GeV/c. Three away-side integration ranges...

Figure 6c: I_{AA} as a function of ξ for direct photon p_T^0 of 5-7, 7-9, and 9-12 GeV/c. Three away-side integration ranges...

Figure 7: Ratios of I_{AA} as a function of direct photon p_T for three different away-side integration ranges.

Figure 2: 10.17182/hepdata.101752.v1.1

Per-trigger yield of hadrons associated to direct photons in Au+Au collisions for direct photon p_T 5-9 GeV/c, compared with p+p baseline, in various ξ bins.

Resources: https://www.hepdata.net/record

cmenergies 200.0 phrases mid-rapidity transverse momentum photon-hadron correlations reactions AU AU

Table with columns for Delta phi [rad] bins (2.0 < xi < 2.4, 1.6 < xi < 2.0, 1.2 < xi < 1.6, 0.8 < xi < 1.2, 0.4 < xi < 0.8, 0.0 < xi < 0.4) and rows for various Delta phi [rad] values. Each cell contains a value with error bars and a percentage.

Why upload to [HEPData](#)?

- Centrally maintained database used by particle physics and LHC experiments
- Reduces reliance on websites maintained by collaborations
- Generates a DOI which results in a **permanent** link to the data
- Improves discoverability of the PHENIX data
- Makes implementation of analysis in [Rivet](#) easier
- You are required to when you publish a paper

HEPData workflow in PHENIX

- Please see the “Procedure” section of the HEPData page on the PHENIX site:
<https://phenixcollaboration.github.io/web/results/hepdata.html>
- HEPData submission packages are produced by researchers, and certified by the respective IRC
- The IRC contact should be added in a comment line in the submission file
- We are using a GitHub repository to manage the formatted material:
<https://github.com/PhenixCollaboration/documentation/tree/master/assets/hepdata>
- The PHENIX DAP team takes care of the upload and coordination
- Take a look at simple examples:
<https://github.com/PhenixCollaboration/documentation/tree/master/assets/hepdata/examples>

HEPData.net

Assignment: Make a HEPData account

Click on link to sandbox. Package all YAML files in a tar ball or zip file.

I recommend iteratively adding each table. Errors are not always useful. The most common errors are related to Latex. Picky about white space.

For legacy analyses, I advocate minimizing time debugging formatting and focusing on getting something accurate and clear up.

Upload an archive to the sandbox

This is a private upload area.

Upload an archive (.zip, .tar, .tar.gz, .tgz) containing YAML files formatted according to these guidelines. An example submission archive is available here. You can validate your YAML files offline using this script.

We also accept a single YAML file containing all of the submission data. For records uploaded to the old HepData site, this format can be obtained automatically by appending "/yaml" to the old record URL.

Alternatively, upload a single text file with extension .oldhepdata containing the "input" format that was used for data submissions from the old HepData site (see sample).

1208.2254.tgz Choose file

Upload and Process

Your sandbox submissions

- BNL-RHIC. We report high statistics measurements of inclusive charged hadro...
2020-04-07 12:32PM
- BNL-RHIC. We report high statistics measurements of inclusive charged hadro...
2020-04-02 15:32PM
- BNL-RHIC. We report high statistics measurements of inclusive charged hadro...
2020-04-02 15:30PM
- BNL-RHIC. We report high statistics measurements of inclusive charged hadro...
2020-04-02 15:25PM

Validation error encountered

A number of errors were encountered by our [validation](#) code. Our validation ensures that your submission files match the format described [here](#). You can validate your YAML files offline using [this script](#).

Please fix your submission and reupload via the associated [record page](#).

fig11.yaml

error Uncertainties should not all be zero in ('errors': [{'symerror': 0, 'label': '\$p_{T}\$ Uncorr'}, {'symerror': 0, 'label': '\$p_{T}\$ Corr'}, {'symerror': 0, 'label': 'Global'}], 'value': 0)

fig21.yaml

error There was a problem parsing the file, while parsing a block mapping in "/opt/hepdata/var/data/1588150448/1588149686/1208.2254/fig21.yaml", line 2, column 3 did not find expected key in "/opt/hepdata/var/data/1588150448/1588149686/1208.2254/fig21.yaml", line 5, column 5

Additional Resources

Abstract (data abstract)

BNL-RHIC. The PHENIX experiment has measured the production of neutral pions in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}}=200$ GeV. The new data offer a fourfold increase in recorded luminosity, providing higher precision and a larger reach in transverse momentum, p_T , to 20 GeV/c. The production ratio of η/π^0 is $0.46 \pm 0.01(\text{stat}) \pm 0.05(\text{sys})$, constant with p_T and collision centrality. The observed ratio is consistent with earlier measurements, as well as with the p-p and d+Au values. The production of π^0 is suppressed by a factor of 5, as in earlier findings. However, with the improved statistical precision a small but significant rise of the nuclear modification factor, R_{AA} , vs p_T , with a slope of $0.0106^{+0.0034}_{-0.0029} [\text{GeV}/c]^{-1}$, is discernible in central collisions. A phenomenological extraction of the average fractional parton energy loss shows a decrease with increasing p_T . To study the path length dependence of suppression, the π^0 yield was measured at different angles with respect to the event plane; a strong azimuthal dependence of the $\pi^0 R_{AA}$ is observed. The data are compared to theoretical models of parton energy loss as a function of the path length, L , in the medium. Models based on pQCD are insufficient to describe the data, while a hybrid model utilizing pQCD for the hard interactions and AdS/CFT for the soft interactions is consistent with the data.

Download All

Filter 10 data tables

- Figure 8 η/π^0 ratios
- Figure 11 π^0 nuclear modification factors
- Figure 20-1 π^0 nuclear modification factors vs reaction plane, $\Delta\phi = 0^\circ - 15^\circ$
- Figure 20-2 π^0 nuclear modification factors vs reaction plane, $\Delta\phi = 15^\circ - 30^\circ$
- Figure 20-3 π^0 nuclear modification factors vs reaction plane, $\Delta\phi = 30^\circ - 45^\circ$
- Figure 20-4 π^0 nuclear modification factors vs reaction plane, $\Delta\phi = 45^\circ - 60^\circ$
- Figure 20-5 π^0 nuclear modification factors vs reaction plane, $\Delta\phi = 60^\circ - 75^\circ$
- Figure 20-6 π^0 nuclear modification factors vs reaction plane, $\Delta\phi = 75^\circ - 90^\circ$

Centrality dependence of p_T ingenerated $R_{AA}(\Delta\phi)$

cmenergies 200.0 reactions AU AU --> NEUTRAL X

N_{part}	$(6 < p_T < 10 \text{ GeV}/c), (0 < \Delta\phi < 15)$	$(6 < p_T < 10 \text{ GeV}/c), (75 < \Delta\phi < 90)$	$(p_T > 10 \text{ GeV}/c), (0 < \Delta\phi < 15)$
N_{part}	$R_{AA}(p_T, \Delta\phi)$		
0 - 10	$0.2123 \pm 0.002549 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0017 \text{ Syst}$	$0.1766 \pm 0.0022 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0018 \text{ Syst}$	$0.2428 \pm 0.0022 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0018 \text{ Syst}$
10 - 20	$0.3063 \pm 0.003552 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.002 \text{ Syst}$	$0.2241 \pm 0.0029 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0021 \text{ Syst}$	$0.3371 \pm 0.0029 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0021 \text{ Syst}$
20 - 30	$0.4113 \pm 0.005015 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0031 \text{ Syst}$	$0.2821 \pm 0.0039 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0031 \text{ Syst}$	$0.4306 \pm 0.0039 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0031 \text{ Syst}$
30 - 40	$0.5439 \pm 0.007235 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0047 \text{ Syst}$	$0.3308 \pm 0.0053 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0046 \text{ Syst}$	$0.5368 \pm 0.0053 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0046 \text{ Syst}$
40 - 50	$0.6809 \pm 0.0109 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0092 \text{ Syst}$	$0.4168 \pm 0.008 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0092 \text{ Syst}$	$0.6676 \pm 0.008 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.0092 \text{ Syst}$
50 - 60	$0.8819 \pm 0.01744 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.016 \text{ Syst}$	$0.4605 \pm 0.011 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.017 \text{ Syst}$	$0.8886 \pm 0.011 \text{ Stat} \pm 0.017 \text{ Syst}$

Visualize

Sum errors Log Scale (Y)

Deselect variables or hide different error bars by clicking on them.

Variables

$R_{AA}(p_T, \Delta\phi)$
 $N_{part} (6 < p_T < 10 \text{ GeV}/c), (0 < \Delta\phi < 15)$
 Summed error

Assignment:

Enter this in a browser window.

<https://www.hepdata.net/download/submission/ins1798493/1/original>

This will download the zip file from a working entry. Then upload it to the sandbox.

Submission.yaml

Gives supplemental materials, determines the order of tables

Figure1.yaml

Gives data points

Figure2.yaml

Figure3.yaml

Figure4.yaml

Semi-automated procedure

Text files with data

Data from the publication:

"Suppression of Hadrons with Large Transverse Momentum in Central Au-Au Collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 130$ GeV",
Adcox et al.,
Phys. Rev. Lett., 88, 022301 (2001),
arXiv:nucl-ex/0309003

Figure 1:

FIG. 1. The yields per event at mid-rapidity for charged hadrons (left) and neutral pions (right) are shown as a function of p_T for 0%-8% (lower) and 9%-30% (upper) event samples.

Lead-Scintillator π^0 peripheral 00-80%							
p_T	$d^2N/d^2\eta/d\phi/dy$ ($\sqrt{s_{NN}}=130$)	σ_{had} (stat)	σ_{had} (sys,uncor)	σ_{had} (sys,cor)	σ_{had} (sys,tot)	$d^2N/d^2\eta/d\phi/dy$ ($\sqrt{s_{NN}}=130$)	σ_{had} (sys,tot)
1.250	0.133947	0.005902	0.003162	0.008992	0.039991		
1.710	0.018260	0.008992	0.002072	0.002739	0.004139		
2.221	0.003480	0.000500	0.000172	0.000180	0.000180		
2.721	0.000690	0.000090	0.000144	0.000184	0.000180		
3.233	0.000251	0.000046	0.000050	0.000030	0.000030		

Moderate manipulation

YAML_Maker

How to make HEPData input

A how-to guide designed for legacy analyses
There are many ways to do this. My goal here is to show you the quickest.

Moderate formatting

HEPData

- Inconsistent format
- Sometimes messy, unclear

- Requires human input

- Easy to install & used
- [On github](#)
- 13 minute [Tutorial](#)
- Or try <https://gitlab.com/cholmcc/hepdata>

- Needs header file, proof-reading

- Some additional requirements for experimental approval, rivet compatibility
- 2-20 hours/paper

Download and install YAMLMaker

Github repository: https://github.com/tkrobatsch/YAML_Maker

Assignment:

Log in to RCF

```
source /cvmfs/sft.cern.ch/lcg/contrib/gcc/8.2.0/x86_64-centos7-gcc8-opt/setup.csh
source /cvmfs/sft.cern.ch/lcg/views/LCG_97python3/x86_64-centos7-gcc8-opt/setup.csh
git clone https://github.com/tkrobatsch/YAML_Maker.git
cd YAML_Maker/
make
```

The YAML files for upload to HEPData are just formatted text files. `YAML_Maker` takes simple text files with the data and makes them into correctly formatted YAML files.

Shout out to undergraduate Tom Krobatsch!

Note that [hepdata-converter](#) is also available. It is dependent on ROOT6 and somewhat dependent on python versions. I have not found it as easy to use.

There is also <https://gitlab.com/cholmcc/hepdata> .

Format text files with data

PHENIX papers are [here](#)

(internal link only)

Example:

PHENIX Phys. Rev. C 87, 034911 (2013)

arxiv:1208.2254

Inspire 1127262

PPG133

Data are available [here](#)

Header

```
$p_T$ x-axis  
4 Number of data sets  
$\eta/\pi^{0}$ y-axis - data set 1  
$\eta/\pi^{0}$ y-axis - data set 2  
$\eta/\pi^{0}$ y-axis - data set 3  
$\eta/\pi^{0}$ y-axis - data set 4  
$0-20\%$ centrality label - data set 1  
$20-60\%$ centrality label - data set 2  
$60-93\%$ centrality label - data set 3  
$0-93\%$ centrality label - data set 4  
yes bins? You want to use bins for Rivet implementation!  
none x statistical uncertainty (symmetric, asymmetric, none)  
none x systematic uncertainty (symmetric, asymmetric, none)  
3 Number of uncertainties?  
$p_{T}$ Uncorr Uncertainty 1 label  
symmetric Unc. 1 type (symmetric, asymmetric, none)  
$p_{T}$ Corr Uncertainty 2 label  
symmetric Unc. 2 type (symmetric, asymmetric, none)  
$p_{T}$ typeC Uncertainty 3 label  
symmetric Unc. 3 type (symmetric, asymmetric, none)
```

Latex accepted, but this is often the cause of errors!

Format text files with data

PHENIX papers are [here](#)

(internal link only)

Example:

PHENIX Phys. Rev. C 87, 034911 (2013)

arxiv:1208.2254

Inspire 1127262

PPG133

Data are available [here](#)

Body

Note: since this was first written and the tutorial was recorded, the formatting for bins was changed from a dash to a space, so it now bin edges should appear as two separate columns.

x range	y	yerr1	yerr2	yerr3
5 6	0.46194	0.026834	0.048098	0.0069292
6 7	0.41051	0.031577	0.042743	0.0061577
7 8	0.47024	0.039008	0.048961	0.0070536
8 9	0.55552	0.0472	0.052187	0.0083328
9 10	0.44789	0.053741	0.042076	0.0067184
10 12	0.51979	0.049027	0.04883	0.0077969
12 14	0.59078	0.073435	0.055498	0.0088617
14 16	0.28979	0.085438	0.027223	0.0043468
16 18	0.43909	0.13536	0.041248	0.0065863

5 6	0.51477	0.020629	0.053598	0.0077216
6 7	0.53073	0.023336	0.05526	0.0079609
7 8	0.50308	0.026865	0.052381	0.0075462
8 9	0.48272	0.032162	0.045347	0.0072407
9 10	0.5492	0.041658	0.051592	0.0082379
10 12	0.50214	0.040903	0.047172	0.0075322
12 14	0.47711	0.062042	0.04482	0.0071566
14 16	0.34917	0.10502	0.032802	0.0052376
16 18	0.54718	0.21836	0.051403	0.0082077

5 6	0.49549	0.025516	0.051591	0.0074324

Tab delimited

Indication of end of data set

Run YAML_Maker on all text files

```
./yaml_data 0 text/fig8.txt
```

The first argument is the debug level (0=quiet, >0=verbose)

The second argument is the text file.

Assignment:

On RCF from YAML_Maker directory

```
./yaml_data 0 Examples/Input/xbinwitherrors.txt
```

```
./yaml_data 1 Examples/Input/xbinwitherrors.txt
```

Shout out to undergraduate Christal Martin, who formatted these text files!

Examples/Input/xbinwitherrors.yaml

independent_variables:

- header: {name: '\$p_T^h p+p/Au+Au 0-20% Centrality\$'}

values:

- {low: 1, high: 2}

- {low: 2, high: 3}

- {low: 3, high: 5}

} X values

dependent_variables:

- header: {'\$1/N_(trig)dN/dp_t(h)[GeV/c]^(-1)\$'}

qualifiers:

- {name: '\$p_T^h p+p/Au+Au 0-20% Centrality\$', value: 'description'}

values:

- value: 1.44E-01

errors:

- {symerror: 9.93E-03, label: 'stat'}

- {asymerror: {plus: 3.37E-02, minus: -3.47E-02}, label: 'sys'}

- value: 4.22E-02

errors:

- {symerror: 5.47E-03, label: 'stat'}

- {asymerror: {plus: 1.15E-02, minus: -1.25E-02}, label: 'sys'}

- value: 1.55E-02

errors:

- {symerror: 2.07E-03, label: 'stat'}

- {asymerror: {plus: 3.25E-03, minus: -3.26E-03}, label: 'sys'}

} Y values, one set for each data set/column

submission.yaml

Top level file which tells HEPData what to read

comment: | **Abstract: no line breaks and beware Latex-related errors!**

BNL-RHIC. The PHENIX experiment has measured the production of neutral pions in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}}=200$ GeV. The new data offer a fourfold increase in recorded luminosity, providing higher precision and a larger reach in transverse momentum, p_T , to 20 GeV/c. The production ratio of η/π^0 is 0.46 ± 0.01 (stat) ± 0.05 (syst), constant with p_T and collision centrality. The observed ratio is consistent with earlier measurements, as well as with the p+p and d+Au values. The production of π^0 is suppressed by a factor of 5, as in earlier findings. However, with the improved statistical precision a small but significant rise of the nuclear modification factor, R_{AA} , vs p_T , with a slope of $0.0106^{(+0.0034)}_{(-0.0029)} [\text{GeV}/c]^{-1}$, is discernible in central collisions. A phenomenological extraction of the average fractional parton energy loss shows a decrease with increasing p_T . To study the path length dependence of suppression, the π^0 yield was measured at different angles with respect to the event plane; a strong azimuthal dependence of the $\pi^0 R_{AA}$ is observed. The data are compared to theoretical models of parton energy loss as a function of the path length, L , in the medium. Models based on pQCD are insufficient to describe the data, while a hybrid model utilizing pQCD for the hard interactions and AdS/CFT for the soft interactions is consistent with the data.

additional_resources:

- {location: "https://www.phenix.bnl.gov/phenix/WWW/info/data/ppg133_data.html", description: "web page with data points"}

--- **Figure delimiter**

name: "Figure 5" **This is how the table is labeled. No latex allowed. Cannot repeat table names.**

description: 'Invariant yields of neutral pions, all centralities' **Figure caption**

keywords:

- {name: reactions, values: [AU AU --> NEUTRAL X]}

- {name: cmenergies, values: [200.0]}

data_file: fig5.yaml

Please populate this! It isn't visible, but it helps make the data searchable.

Image thumbnails

To include images and thumbnails, download the image file (example: fig1.png) and put it into the yaml folder. Make a copy and rename it as thumb_fig1.png. In the submission file, include the following additional resources (“location” & ”description”) for each image file:

```
---
additional_resources:
- {description: Image file, location: Raa.png}
- {description: Thumbnail Image file, location: thumb_Raa.png}
data_file: xbinwitherrors.yaml
description: Pups save the analysis logic
keywords:
- name: reactions
  values: [P P --> N X]
- name: observables
  values: [ASYM]
- name: cmenergies
  values: [200.0]
name: Figure 1a
```

Must start with “thumb_”

In the PHENIX hepdata repository, there is a script `scripts/makethumbnails.pl` which copies every `.png` to `thumb_[filename].png`. There is also a script which converts all eps files in a given directory to a png with reasonable resolution.

Run a test

Assignment:

On RCF from YAML_Maker directory

```
cd Examples
```

```
tar -czvf test.tgz submission.yaml xbinwitherrors.yaml *.png
```

Transfer test.tgz to your laptop and upload it to the sandbox.

```
# PHENIX paper PPG000
#
# Paw Patrol is on a roll
#
# Phys. Rev. C 69, 034909 (2004)
# InspireHEP ID: 1658594
#
# Prepared by Marshall
# Please contact Ryder if you have any questions about this submission
# PPG liaison: Skye
# Reviewer: Everest
#
```

```
additional_resources:
```

- {description: Image file, location: Raa.png}
- {description: web page with data points, location: 'https://phenix-intra.sdcc.bnl.gov/phenix/WWW/info/data/ppg238_data.html'}
- {description: arXiv link, location: 'https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.14187'}

```
comment: |
```

```
  BNL-RHIC. Ryder and his team of pups are here to save the day. Paw Patrol is on a roll.
```

```
---
```

```
additional_resources:
```

- {description: Image file, location: Raa.png}
- {description: Thumbnail Image file, location: thumb_Raa.png}

```
data_file: xbinwitherrors.yaml
```

```
description: Pups save the analysis logic
```

```
keywords:
```

- name: reactions
 values: [P P --> N X]
- name: observables
 values: [ASYM]
- name: cmenergies
 values: [200.0]

```
name: Figure 1a
```

```
---
```

```
additional_resources:
```

- {description: Image file, location: Raa.png}
- {description: Thumbnail Image file, location: thumb_Raa.png}

```
data_file: xbinwitherrors.yaml
```

Header. Does not appear on
HEPData but helps with logistics
of submission.

Tips

This is not the time or place to express your creativity!

Start with a minimal working example. Add data iteratively and test often using the sandbox.

Use bins - it will pay off during Rivet implementation

Don't worry too much about Latex formatting

Sample files: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ZFqggDSwQmH2XjxXKqk5ro327wKYgCgd?usp=sharing>

Note: the final step is for the collaboration's designated HEPData coordinator to approve the submission, after it has been checked by the IRC.

Numerical precision: `scripts/formatter.py` in hepdata repository is useful for formatting numbers.

Qualifiers

Note that `YAML_Maker` does not handle these correctly as of today.

Qualifiers are supposed to provide limits for things like kinematic variables.

These will have to be fixed by hand.

Hide Publication Information

Additional Resources

Abstract (data abstract)

BNL-RHIC. We present measurements of azimuthal correlations of charged hadron pairs in $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200$ GeV Au+Au collisions for the trigger and associated particle transverse-momentum ranges of $1 < p_T^t < 10$ -GeV/c and $0.5 < p_T^a < 10$ -GeV/c. After subtraction of an underlying event using a model that includes higher-order azimuthal anisotropy v_2, v_3 , and v_4 , the away-side yield of the highest trigger- p_T ($p_T^t > 4$ -GeV/c) correlations is suppressed compared to that of correlations measured in $p+p$ collisions. At the lowest associated particle p_T ($0.5 < p_T^a < 1$ GeV/c), the away-side shape and yield are modified relative to those in $p+p$ collisions. These observations are consistent with the scenario of radiative-jet energy loss. For the low- p_T trigger correlations ($2 < p_T^t < 4$ GeV/c), a finite away-side yield exists and we explore the dependence of the shape of the away-side within the context of an underlying-event model. Correlations are also studied differentially versus

Upload New Files

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Filter 33 data tables

Figure 6

Higher-order flow harmonics for charged hadrons at midrapidity in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}}$ and their systematics: v_2, v_3, v_4 , and...

Figure 12

Per-trigger yields $Y(\Delta\phi)$ of dihadrons pairs measured in Au+Au collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}}$ after subtracting the underlying event model with several p_T ...

Figure 15

Per-trigger yields $Y(\Delta\phi)$ of dihadron pairs measured in Au+

p_T^{trig}	2-4		4-10	2-4		4-10
p_T^{assoc}	1-2	2-4		1-2	2-4	
$ \Delta\phi - \pi _{max}$	$\pi/4$					
centrality	0-10%			10-20%		
$\phi^a - \psi_2$	$\int Y d\Delta\phi$					
-1.5708 - -1.1781	0.06 ±0.009 stat	0.006 ±0.0016 stat	0.016 ±0.001 stat	0.07 ±0.007 stat	0.008 ±0.0012 stat	0.01 ±0.001 stat
	±0.029 sys	±0.0035 sys	±0.016 sys	±0.024 sys	±0.005 sys	±0.001 sys
	±0.0018 ZYAM	±0.0005 ZYAM	±0.007 ZYAM	±0.0026 ZYAM	±0.00033 ZYAM	±0.0003 ZYAM
-1.1781 - -0.785398	0.009 ±0.009 stat	0.0013 ±0.0016 stat	0.0024 ±0.001 stat	0.0028 ±0.007 stat	0.0005 ±0.0013 stat	0.0003 ±0.0003 stat
	±0.028 sys	±0.004 sys	±0.016 sys	±0.027 sys	±0.004 sys	±0.001 sys
	±0.0019 ZYAM	±0.0005 ZYAM	±0.007 ZYAM	±0.0030 ZYAM	±0.0004 ZYAM	±0.0003 ZYAM

Visualize

Sum errors Log Scale (X)

Log Scale (Y)

Show all

Figure yaml

independent_variables:

- header: {name: '\$\phi^a-\psi_2\$'}
values:
 - {low: -1.5708, high: -1.1781}
 - {low: -1.1781, high: -0.785398}
 - {low: -0.785398, high: -0.392699}
 - {low: -0.392699, high: 0}

dependent_variables:

- header: {\$\int Y d\Delta \phi\$}
qualifiers:
 - {name: '\$p_{T}^{\text{trig}}\$', value: '2-4'}
 - {name: '\$p_{T}^{\text{assoc}}\$', value: '1-2'}
 - {name: '\$|\Delta\phi|_{\text{max}}\$', value: '\$\pi/4\$'}
 - {name: 'centrality', value: '0-10%'}values:
 - value: 0.12errors:
 - {symerror: 0.009, label: 'stat'}
 - {symerror: 0.03, label: 'sys'}
 - {symerror: 0.0018, label: 'ZYAM'}
 - value: 0.07

Qualifiers - must have same names and same set of qualifiers for every data set or formatting will not be correct. Values can be different.

YAML_Maker features

YAML_Maker lets you format data with uncertainties on the x-axis. HEPData does not accept these values, so this is not a useful feature.

YAML_Maker does not accept text values on the x-axis, but HEPData does.

YAML_Maker requires every single column in a table to have the same number and format of uncertainties. HEPData does not.

Requirements for Rivet

- Need to have data binned - Rivet treats the model like data
 - Bins cannot overlap
- X-axis must have an independent variable
 - For example, v_2 vs N_{ch} would not work
- Use centrality instead of model-dependent variables (N_{part} , N_{bin})
 - Can list N_{part} , N_{bin} as an extra “data set” for completeness

PHENIX data

For technical reasons, the old PHENIX web site with data posted can no longer be public.

PHENIX collaborators can access the data on the internal web site here:

<https://phenix-intra.sdcc.bnl.gov//WWW/talk/papers.php>

People outside of PHENIX should contact the Data and Analysis Preservation team phenix-dap-l@lists.bnl.gov

PHENIX-specific HEPData instructions, including information on keywords, are here <https://phenixcollaboration.github.io/web/results/hepdata.html>

Getting old data

PHENIX

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